

Early Studies of Mechanisms of Racemization of Octahedral Metal Complexes

FRED BASOLO

Department of Chemistry, Northwestern University, Evanston, IL 60208, U.S.A.

An overview is given of research done in the fifties on the kinetics and mechanisms of racemization of $[M(AA)_6]^{2+}$ ($M = Ni, Fe$; $(AA) = 2,2'$ -bipyridine, 1,10-phenanthroline). The nickel(II) complexes racemize by a ligand dissociation mechanism, but the iron(II) complexes racemize both by a dissociation and an intramolecular pathway. The intramolecular mechanism for $[Fe(phen)_3]^{2+}$ is believed to take place without Fe-N bond rupture, perhaps by a twist process of the type first proposed by the late Professor P. Ray, a student of P. C. Ray. The rates of acid dissociation of the 1,10-phenanthroline complexes is independent of acid concentration but that of the 2,2'-bipyridine complexes increase in rate with increasing acid concentration. At some high acid concentration the rate becomes constant, and this is believed to be a measure of the rate of M-N bond cleavage.

RAY and Dutt¹ were the first to suggest a twist mechanism, without metal-ligand bond cleavage, for the racemization of octahedral complexes of the type $[M(AA)_6]$ ($(AA) = \text{any bidentate chelating ligand}$). The late Professor P. Ray (student of Professor P. C. Ray who is being honored by this special issue of the journal) achieved international acclaim for his outstanding research in coordination chemistry, and his best known contribution is that of the rhombic twist mechanism for racemization of $[M(AA)_6]$ complexes. This concept of intramolecular racemization, without metal-ligand bond rupture, predates by two decades the modern well-known version of fluxional molecules².

In the forties as a graduate student of Professor John C. Bailar, Jr., I had occasion to read some of the elegant papers of the late Professor Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray, and of his student Priyadarajan Ray. Fortunately during the 1979 ICCS in Calcutta honoring P. Ray, I was finally able to meet him at his home and tell him how much I appreciated his research and that of his mentor P. C. Ray. I am pleased to be invited to write an article for a special issue of the *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society*, in commemoration of the 125th birthday of P. C. Ray. The research we did that would be of greatest interest to Professor Ray is our studies of the mechanism of racemization of $[M(AA)_6]^{2+}$ ($M = Ni, Fe$; $(AA) = 2,2'$ -bipyridine, 1,10-phenanthroline). This work as reported in the fifties, but most chemists now have no knowledge of it so I will just give a brief overview of the research and indicate how it relates to the Ray and Dutt¹ twist mechanism.

As early as 1912 Werner³ proposed an intramolecular process for the racemization of $[M(AA)_6]$ complexes involving the rupture of a metal-ligand bond (eq. 1).

If the structure of the five-coordinate intermediate is trigonal bipyramid, then chirality is lost. A decade later Thomas⁴ suggested a dissociation mechanism for the racemization of oxalato complexes of the type $[M(C_2O_4)_3]^{3-}$ (eq. 2).

Regardless of the structure of the intermediate, if symmetrical, the process results in racemization. It was later shown⁵ that dissociation accounts for the racemization of substitution labile $[M(C_2O_4)_3]^{3-}$ ($M = Al, Fe$), but not of substitution inert ($M = Co, Cr, Rh$). The first suggestion of an intramolecular mechanism of racemization, without metal ligand bond cleavage was reported by Ray and Dutt¹ (eq. 3).

This rhombic twist mechanism leads to a symmetrical intermediate, and loss of optical activity.

Our investigations of the mechanisms of racemization of metal complexes commenced with a

kinetic study of aqueous acid solutions of chiral $[\text{Ni}(\text{AA})_3]^{2+}$ ((AA) = bipy, ophen). Working with my colleague at the time, Professor Henry Neumann, we decided to extend the studies reported by Davies and Dwyer⁶ on the rates of racemization of these nickel complexes. They concluded the complexes racemize by an intramolecular process, because the rates of racemization were not altered by the presence of free excess chelating ligand. We decided this need not be correct, for if the dissociated products were either symmetrical or lost its optical activity very rapidly then the presence of added bidentate ligand would not change the rates of racemization. To test this idea, kinetic studies were made at the same experimental condition of the kinetics of racemization and of acid dissociation (eq. 4)⁷

Comparison of the rates of racemization and dissociation under the same conditions shows them to be equal within experimental error. This is best illustrated in Fig. 1, which shows plots of $\log k$ (obtained

Fig. 1. Temperature dependence of reactions of $[\text{Ni}(\text{ophen})_3]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{bipy})_3]^{2+}$: (O) racemization and (□) dissociation; (I) $[\text{Ni}(\text{ophen})_3]^{2+}$ and (II) $[\text{Ni}(\text{bipy})_3]^{2+}$.

from both racemization and dissociation) vs $1/T$. All the data for $[\text{Ni}(\text{ophen})_3]^{2+}$ fall on the same straight line, giving an activation energy of $25.0 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. The same value is obtained for the racemization in water, and the dissociation in 5 M HCl , and is in agreement with the value reported by Davies and Dwyer⁶.

It is quite clear then that in these acid solutions the racemization proceeds via dissociation. The question then arises as to whether this is still true in

neutral solution where the dissociation cannot be measured. The fact that the activation energies for dissociation in acid and for racemization in water are the same would indicate there is no change in mechanism with acidity. The continuous behavior of the two rates as a function of acidity is also consistent with this interpretation. This continuity is most apparent for $[\text{Ni}(\text{ophen})_3]^{2+}$, where k for racemization shows only little variation with acid strength, the influence of hydrogen ion probably resulting only from a salt-effect. The dissociation and racemization of $[\text{Ni}(\text{bipy})_3]^{2+}$ show a pronounced acid dependence, the acid dependence of the racemization at low acidities having been demonstrated previously⁸. It might be pointed out that the behavior of $[\text{Ni}(\text{bipy})_3]^{2+}$ is similar to the dissociation behavior of $[\text{Fe}(\text{bipy})_3]^{2+}$ reported by Baxendale and George⁹. It seems reasonable to conclude that racemization results from dissociation over the entire acid range.

In regard to the actual configuration of the complex ion resulting from dissociation, several hypotheses are consistent with the observations. The only limitation on such a species is that it be either optically inactive, or that it loses its activity rapidly with respect to the rate at which recombination occurs. This restriction is imposed by the observation that excess complexing agent does not affect the rate of racemization, as mentioned earlier. If the intermediate is optically active and itself racemizes by a first-order reaction, we estimate the half-time for this reaction need only be less than 2 s to account for the failure of excess ligand to change the rate of racemization.

Davies and Dwyer⁶ also reported that the activation energies and the entropies of activation for the racemization of $[\text{Fe}(\text{AA})_3]^{2+}$ are larger than of $[\text{Ni}(\text{AA})_3]^{2+}$, but concluded both racemize by an intramolecular process. Brown *et al.*¹⁰ inferred that a dissociation mechanism is involved because of the near-equivalence of the Fe^{II} exchange rates¹¹ and the racemization rates of the iron complexes. However, since the Fe^{II} exchange was done only qualitatively at room temperature, a better comparison to make would be with the quantitative values for the rates of dissociation^{8,9}. Such a comparison reveals that the rate of racemization is in fact faster than the rate of dissociation and thus not consistent with a dissociation mechanism. Unfortunately, these independent experiments were not carried out at the same conditions and the differences in rate may be due to secondary effects such as ionic strength or acid concentration. It was, therefore, necessary that we^{2,3} investigate the kinetics of these reactions under exactly the same experimental conditions.

This investigation was carried out in acid solutions so that the racemization results obtained might be compared with the rates of dissociation. The observation of an acid-independent dissociation for $[\text{Fe}(\text{ophen})_3]^{2+}$ and an acid-dependent dissociation

for $[\text{Fe}(\text{bipy})_3]^{2+}$ is the same as that for the corresponding Ni^{II} complexes⁷. This is explained in terms of the 2,2'-bipyridine ligand being flexible, so that M-N bond rupture can take place and the free N being trapped by a proton to retard return to the closed chelate ring. At some high acid concentration, the rate no longer increases with increasing acid concentration which then is the rate of M-N bond cleavage. The rigid $\text{M}(\text{ophen})$ chelate ring does not permit an uncoordinated N, thus the rate of dissociation does not depend on acid.

The rates of racemization of the Fe^{II} complexes mirror the rates of acid dissociation, but racemization is faster than dissociation (Table 1). From the results obtained on the racemization of the related Ni^{II} complexes⁷ it is a reasonable assumption that each dissociation leads to loss of optical activity. Table 1 lists the rate of dissociation corresponding to the experimental conditions of the racemization, these rates being obtained from our experimental rates of dissociation corrected for temperature differences where necessary. The fact that the racemization is more rapid than the dissociation implies that racemization also takes place by some intramolecular or non-dissociative process. The observed rate of racemization will then be the sum of the two rates, and obviously the rate of intramolecular racemization can be obtained by subtracting the rate of dissociation from the total rate. These results are also given in Table 1. The activation energies for the intramolecular process can be determined from the data, and they are 29 ± 2 kcal mol^{-1} for $[\text{Fe}(\text{ophen})_3]^{2+}$ and 26 ± 2 kcal mol^{-1} for $[\text{Fe}(\text{bipy})_3]^{2+}$.

TABLE 1

Rate of racemization of tris(1,10-phenanthroline)iron(II) ion				
Solution	Temp.	$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		
HCl	°C	k_{obs}	k_{diss}	k_{intramol}
M				
1.0	16	9.9	0.8	9.1
1.0	25	4.0	4.0	9.6
Rate of racemization of tris(2,2'-bipyridine)iron(II)				
Solution	Temp.	$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		
HCl	°C	k_{obs}	k_{diss}	k_{intramol}
M				
1.5	16.0	1.82	1.26	0.56
1.5	25.0	6.43	4.79	1.64
0.25	25.0	5.56	2.56	3.00
0.5	25.0	6.05	3.90	2.15
1.0	25.0	6.41	4.69	1.72
2.0	25.0	6.40	4.70	1.70

The detailed mechanisms of intramolecular rearrangements are still not known¹³. However, it is agreed that this either takes place by means of one chelate group opening up at one end (eq. 1), or by the chelate rings shifting around the central metal atom (eqs. 3 and 5).

This trigonal (Bailar) twist¹⁴, like the rhombic twist¹, gives a symmetrical intermediate and provides a pathway for racemization.

In the case of the intramolecular rearrangement of $[\text{Fe}(\text{ophen})_3]^{2+}$ there can be no opening of the chelate rings. This is necessarily true because of the geometry of the 1,10-phenanthroline molecule which is a fixed planar structure with the nitrogen atoms only approximately 2.5 Å apart. Therefore, this molecule cannot behave as a monodentate group and the intramolecular process must involve the movement of these chelate rings about the central atom. We would expect this process to be independent of acidity, and this is the case, since both the total rate of racemization and the rate of dissociation are independent of acidity.

The $\text{Fe}(\text{bipy})_3]^{2+}$ can conceivably undergo intramolecular racemization in two ways. One would be like that of $[\text{Fe}(\text{ophen})_3]^{2+}$ which involves shifting, but not breaking, of Fe-N bonds. This process would be acid independent. The second would involve an intramolecular racemization of

Since the life time of this species would decrease with increasing acid concentration, it follows that racemization through such a route decreases with increasing acidity, and approaches zero at high acidities. Examination of the change in the intramolecular rate shows that it decreases with acidity but does not reach zero, indicating that both intramolecular mechanisms are operative.

Why should these very similar Ni^{II} and Fe^{II} complexes racemize by different mechanisms? Perhaps the answer is found in their difference in bonding. The Ni^{II} complexes are high-spin d^8 systems, while the Fe^{II} complexes are low-spin d^6 systems. This means that the low-spin Fe^{II} complexes may go to an excited high-spin state prior to dissociation (eq. 6).

The high spin excited state may have longer Fe-N bond distances and permit racemization¹⁵ before returning to the low-spin ground state. Thus if $k_2 > k_3$ the racemization takes place intramolecularly, but if $k_2 < k_3$ an intermolecular process is involved. The results for Fe^{II} complexes show that $k_2 \sim k_3$, so both mechanisms contribute to the observed rates of racemization.

Further studies from our laboratory on the racemization of these $\text{Fe}^{II,III}$ complexes include studies on (i) the effect of added ions¹⁶, (ii) the

effect of solvent¹⁷, and (iii) the effect of added large ions¹⁸. The results of these studies were in accord with the mechanisms proposed, but differences in rates of the dissociative and the intramolecular pathways were observed.

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